

**THE REFLECTION OF CULTURE ON PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK**

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Annotation: This paper explores the connection between phraseological units (PUs) and culture, with a comparative analysis of Russian and Uzbek examples. Drawing on theories by V.N. Telia, A.A. Koonin, and others, it demonstrates how PUs encapsulate cultural values, historical experiences, and collective cognitive patterns, serving as cultural markers of each society.

Keywords: Phraseological units, culture, cognitive linguistics, Russian, Uzbek, cultural reflection, metaphor, V.N. Telia, A.A. Koonin, collective memory, language and culture, idiomatic expressions.

Introduction. Phraseological units (PhUs) are not merely linguistic expressions but complex reflections of the culture, worldview, and cognitive patterns of the societies in which they are used. These fixed expressions often transcend the literal meaning of their components, providing insight into the shared beliefs, history, and social norms of a language community. This paper aims to explore how cultural elements are encoded in phraseological units in two distinct linguistic traditions: Russian and Uzbek. Both languages have rich phraseological repertoires that reflect their historical ties, societal structures, and cultural values. By comparing Russian and Uzbek phraseological units, we can uncover how these languages serve as vessels for transmitting cultural knowledge across generations.

Materials and Methods. This study is grounded in both theoretical and empirical approaches to linguistics. Numerous methods have been analyzed while composing this research, however the mostly active approaches are admitted as the following:

Corpus Analysis: A comparative corpus of phraseological units in Russian and Uzbek will be compiled, using dictionaries, linguistic corpora, and examples from literary sources.

Theoretical Framework: The analysis will draw from the theories of prominent linguists who have studied the relationship between culture and language. The main theoretical contributions include the works of V.N. Telia, A. Abdugafurov, and cognitive linguistics theories on metaphor and cultural cognition.

Comparative Linguistic Analysis: The focus will be on analyzing cultural connotations within these PUs and examining how their meanings reflect the cultural mindset of Russian and Uzbek speakers.

The idea that phraseological units encapsulate the culture of a language community is not new. Several linguistic theories and frameworks highlight this connection between language and culture. As the issue has been considered crucial and actual, a great deal of linguists proposed various theories relating to it. Such as, V.N. Telia's Cognitive Theory of Phraseology, a prominent Russian linguist, argued that phraseological units are not only linguistic constructs but also cognitive entities that reflect a speaker's worldview. According to Telia, phraseological units provide valuable insights into how speakers of a language conceptualize their surroundings, including natural phenomena, social relationships, and psychological states. These expressions are shaped by historical events, social practices, and the collective experience of a community. For Telia, Phraseological Units reflect cultural schemata, which are mental structures that help individuals understand and navigate their world. Thus, the study of phraseological units can reveal much about the cultural and cognitive processes that govern human interaction. Or A.A. Koonin is a significant figure in Russian phraseological studies. In his work, Koonin argues that phraseological units (PUs) reflect the "national picture of the world" (национальная картина мира), which means that PUs serve as a window into how a culture conceptualizes and interprets reality. He suggests that each language encapsulates specific cultural and cognitive

patterns that emerge from historical experiences, social organization, and natural surroundings.

The work of George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, has had a significant impact on the study of phraseology. According to the cognitive linguistics approach, language is fundamentally shaped by human perception, experience, and conceptualization. PUs, then, are seen as reflections of the metaphors and cognitive structures that guide human thought. In cultural linguistics, which is closely tied to cognitive linguistics, researchers study how cultural beliefs, values, and practices influence language. This approach posits that language is a repository of cultural meanings and that metaphorical expressions in language are often rooted in shared cultural experiences. In Uzbek linguistics, A. Abdugafurov's work has been instrumental in understanding the connection between language and culture, particularly in the realm of phraseological units. Abdugafurov highlighted that phraseological units are shaped by the collective experience of the people and serve as a window into the cultural fabric of a society. His approach emphasizes that in the case of Uzbek, many PUs are grounded in Islamic traditions, historical events, and the pastoral and agricultural life that has dominated the region for centuries. Abdugafurov's theory suggests that phraseological units reflect the collective unconscious of a society and can only be fully understood when contextualized within the culture that gave rise to them.

Anna Wierzbicka's theory of cultural scripts focuses on the ways in which specific cultural values are encoded in language. Wierzbicka asserts that languages reflect "cultural scripts"—sets of values and norms that are systematically represented in linguistic expressions. These scripts guide behavior, perceptions, and interactions within a community. In examining phraseological units, we can identify the cultural scripts that underpin everyday language and behavior, from politeness strategies to expressions of respect, love, or conflict.

By applying these theoretical frameworks, this paper will explore how Russian and Uzbek phraseological units encode cultural values such as family structure, social hierarchy, worldview, and perceptions of nature.

Results. Based on the materials we collected, the following phraseological units have been found relevant to prove our assumption:

1 "Как кошка с собакой" (Like a cat and a dog) - To be in constant conflict or disagreement. This expression reflects the long-standing cultural association between cats and dogs in Russian folklore. In traditional Russian beliefs, cats and dogs are often seen as natural enemies, which is mirrored in everyday life and interpersonal dynamics. The phrase emphasizes a cultural value placed on harmony and the tension that can exist in close relationships.

According to V.N. Telia, this phrase reflects the "cognitive schemata" of Russian culture, which has long been characterized by a pragmatic approach to resolving conflict, often by naming the conflict openly.

2. "Не всё коту масленица" (It's not always Shrovetide for the cat) - Good times do not last forever.

- Cultural Reflection: Shrovetide (Maslenitsa) is an ancient Russian festival that marks the end of winter and the arrival of spring. It is a time of feasting and celebration, symbolizing warmth and abundance. This phrase reflects the cyclical nature of life in Russia, where the harshness of winter is often followed by periods of abundance, but these periods are fleeting. The cultural value reflected here is the awareness of the transient nature of joy and prosperity. This phrase embodies the cyclical and seasonal worldview present in Russian culture, a key aspect of Telia's theory of "cultural schemata" in language.

3. "Держать камень за пазухой" (To keep a stone in one's bosom) - To harbor ill intentions or to be secretly hostile. This phrase evokes an image of hidden malice or treachery, which reflects the historical Russian experience of intrigue and political maneuvering. Russian culture has long valued openness and sincerity, so the phrase

captures the sense of betrayal in a society that places a premium on honest interactions. From a cognitive linguistics perspective, this phrase exemplifies the metaphor of "holding something heavy" in the chest, representing the emotional burden of secret hostility.

Uzbek Phraseological Units:

1. "Kechasi qorong'i, kunduzgi yulduz" (A star at night, a star by day) - A person who remains admirable or noteworthy regardless of time or situation. This phrase reflects the Uzbek admiration for consistency and steadfastness, qualities held in high esteem in Uzbek society. It draws upon celestial imagery, symbolizing the unchanging nature of a person's worth, akin to the constancy of the stars. This aligns with the importance of loyalty and honor in Uzbek culture. According to Wierzbicka's theory of cultural scripts, this phrase reflects a deep cultural value of stability and honor, both of which are crucial elements of Uzbek social norms.

2. "Boshiga qora bulut tushmoq" (To have a black cloud on one's head) - To be in trouble or face misfortune. The image of a "black cloud" symbolizes impending misfortune or adversity, a metaphor commonly used across Central Asia to express the vulnerability of individuals to fate. This reflects the broader Uzbek cultural view of life as shaped by destiny and divine will, with people often attributing their fortunes or misfortunes to higher powers. Abdugafurov's perspective on phraseology aligns with this metaphor, suggesting that it reflects the traditional worldview in which fate plays a dominant role.

3. "Tilla so'z" (Golden words) - Wise or highly valuable words of advice. This phrase underscores the Uzbek cultural respect for wisdom, particularly that of elders. In a society where oral traditions and proverbs hold significant importance, the phrase highlights the value placed on advice passed down through generations. This phrase resonates with cognitive linguistics' theory of conceptual metaphors, where wisdom is often equated with precious metals like gold, reflecting the high value placed on knowledge and experience in Uzbek culture.

Both Russian and Uzbek phraseological units reflect their respective societies' values, social structures, and historical experiences. Russian phraseology frequently emphasizes seasonal changes, conflict resolution, and the need for honesty and openness. Conversely, Uzbek phraseology often draws on celestial imagery, divine will, and the enduring nature of wisdom and social bonds. While Russian PUs tend to reflect the harshness of history and the need for resilience, Uzbek PUs emphasize harmony, stability, and respect for the natural order .

The influence of cultural scripts, as outlined by Wierzbicka, is evident in both languages. These cultural scripts guide behavior and language use, encoding the collective values of each society. For example, Russian idioms related to conflict reflect a historical culture of directness and pragmatism, while Uzbek idioms emphasize values of harmony and respect.

Conclusion. The comparative study of Russian and Uzbek phraseological units reveals the deep connection between language and culture. Both languages use phraseological units as cultural vehicles, encoding beliefs, values, and historical experiences into everyday expressions. Understanding these PUs provides valuable insight into the cultural psyche of each society and highlights the importance of language as a mirror of cultural identity.

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